

MANAGEMENT OF NEW STUDENT ADMISSION (PPDB) ZONING SYSTEM IN INCREASING LEARNING OPPORTUNITIES FOR PROSPECTIVE HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN JAKARTA

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Abstract

Admission of new students (PPDB) to the high school zoning system in Jakarta that the zoning system based on the Minister of Education and Culture requires schools to accept prospective students who live in the closest zone radius to the school. This study aims to analyze and describe the planning, organizing, implementation and supervision as well as the impact of the PPDB zoning system for increase the learning opportunities for high school students in Jakarta in the 2022/2023 school year, using a qualitative approach. The research method is a descriptive evaluative method and data collection techniques using interviews, observation and documents. The researcher made direct observations and used guided free interviews. The research object was carried out directly at SMA Negeri 28 and SMA Negeri 70 Jakarta, including. First, place, second, actors, including school principals, vice principals, operators, teachers, students, and parents of students as well as representatives of the government or the surrounding community. Third, activities, namely PPDB zoning system activities in the two schools. The results of this study indicate that the two schools have carried out planning, organizing, implementing and supervising according to existing theory and in accordance with applicable regulations as the Ministry of Education and Culture. The general conclusion is that the management of PPDB zoning system in increasing learning opportunities for prospective high school students in Jakarta has been implemented, both in terms of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising it, although in its implementation it has not fully run optimally according to the expected goals. This is due to limited human resources and other resources as well as a lack of understanding in understanding and implementing the zoning system PPDB in increasing learning opportunities for prospective students.

Keywords: Management, PPDB, Zoning System, Learning Opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

The admission of new students (PPDB) is a crucial initial activity in schools at the beginning of each academic year. The current government policy stipulates that PPDB is carried out through a zoning system or based on the closest geographic conditions to ensure that schools admit at least 90% of prospective students residing closest to the

school. Through this zoning system, prospective students who live near the school are given higher priority, even becoming the top priority with a larger quota. The zoning system of PPDB can increase learning opportunities for all prospective students without discriminating based on economic status, religion, ethnicity, or social group; everyone has the right to receive education appropriate to their level.

The zoning system of PPDB promotes equal access to education for all citizens by preparing schools that are of the same quality as favored schools. Issues related to the unequal quality of education include the lack of educational facilities and infrastructure. According to Novita, cited in Nurviana et al. (2021:82), 88.8% of schools in Indonesia, from elementary to high school, have not reached the minimum service quality standards. Furthermore, based on Kristyaningrum's research (2019:186-195), the challenges faced in implementing the zoning PPDB in Brebes Regency include system errors leading to confusion among dozens of student candidates regarding sudden changes in their residence, the obligation to accept 90% of students living near the school. In addition, research by Pradewi and Rukiyati (2019:4) suggests that zoning simplifies access to educational services, equalizes school quality, reduces school quality, limits student school choices, and zoning policies must be accompanied by the equalization of educational facilities and infrastructure and can damage diversity.

Given these issues, the concept of "Opportunity to Learn" (OTL) is essential, particularly when related to the zoning system in PPDB, as it can measure or evaluate the implementation of the zoning PPDB policy, especially in the management of the zoning PPDB system. According to Suryanti's research (2020; 111–126), the PPDB for the 2017/2018 and 2018/2019 academic years was less effective due to the presence of the Socio-Economic Welfare Cards (SKTM) in PPDB. As a result, students who should have been able to attend schools close to their homes had to go to other schools farther away because they were outcompeted by students using SKTM. This situation highlights issues related to learning opportunities for prospective students living near the school. This issue was addressed with Ministerial Regulation Number 44 of 2019, which eliminated the SKTM route. Challenges in the 2019/2020 PPDB, as researched by Wahyuni (2019;13-18), include a lack of socialization, government unpreparedness in determining school zones, varying understandings among government officials and the public, which did not align with the policy's goals, and the persistence of a dichotomy between favored and non-favored schools.

Moving on to the management of PPDB, it needs to be well-structured and optimally managed. Terry's four management functions, namely planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling (referred to as POAC), are well-known. Given the various issues in the management of the zoning PPDB system, the researcher is interested in conducting research on the management of New Student Admissions (PPDB) in the zoning system to enhance learning opportunities for high school students in Jakarta (a descriptive study at SMA Negeri 28 and SMA Negeri 70 Jakarta).

Therefore, this study aims to describe and analyze the implementation of the zoning PPDB policy in enhancing learning opportunities for students in public high schools in DKI Jakarta. Specifically, the researcher wants to describe and analyze the Planning, Organizing, Acting, and Controlling of the zoning PPDB system in enhancing learning opportunities for prospective students at SMA Negeri 28 and SMA Negeri 70 Jakarta.

George R. Terry, who proposed that management functions consist of four steps, namely planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling, famously known as POAC. George R. Terry (2016: 67) stated that the approach often used in planning involves asking questions whose answers require further study to make the plan more comprehensive. The questions to assist in this planning process include the five W's and one H: why should it be done?, what is needed?, where will it be done?, when will it be done?, who will do it?, and how will it be done?.

Mulyono defines planning as "a rational and systematic activity in making decisions, activities, or steps that will be carried out in the future in order to achieve goals effectively and efficiently" (Mulyono, 2017:25). Planning for the new student admission (PPDB) in the zoning system is the initial step in the management process, involving decisions about what, when, how, and who is involved, carefully considering both the present and future timelines through appropriate strategies and tactics to achieve organizational goals. Planning should be clear and specific in its scope, work programs or plans should be measurable in terms of their success, should consider existing human resources, neither too easy nor too difficult, and should pay attention to timing or target achievement.

The concept of organizing, according to George R. Terry, is the "arrangement of effective behavioral relationships among personnel so that they can work together efficiently and make personal decisions in carrying out tasks in existing environmental situations to achieve specific goals and objectives" (Terry, 2019). Wukir suggests five steps in organizing: reviewing goals and objectives, determining activities that involve preparation and analysis of activities to achieve goals, classifying and grouping activities into smaller working units, assigning and placing the appropriate resources, and evaluating results through feedback to determine whether the strategy is being executed well and whether any changes are needed (Wukir: 2013: 32). School principals and PPDB committees are expected to coordinate activities from setting goals to evaluation by allocating resources appropriately and adhering to the steps of the zoning system PPDB.

Every activity has its intended goals. Similarly, the implementation of the zoning system PPDB in improving the learning opportunities for high school students in Jakarta has specific objectives. As Akdon (2011:186) points out, the purpose of implementation is to achieve goals and objectives through detailed strategies in the form of policies, operational programs, and activities (Akdon 2011:186). According to George R. Terry, controlling is an "effort to examine activities that have been and will be carried out" (Terry, 2019:166).

The new student admission (PPDB) in the zoning system is based on the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2021 regarding PPDB at kindergarten, elementary, junior high, senior high, and vocational schools (RI, 2021), the Governor of DKI Jakarta Regulation Number 32 of 2021 regarding Technical Guidelines for PPDB (Pergub DKI Jakarta, 2021), and the Decree of the Head of the Provincial Education Department of DKI Jakarta Number 466 of 2021 concerning the Process Flow of PPDB Implementation for the 2021/2022 Academic Year, which mandates that the zoning system requires schools to admit prospective students residing within the closest radius of the school (Decision of the Head of the Provincial Education Department of DKI Jakarta, 2021).

The steps in the zoning system PPDB include Planning, Organizing, Implementing, and Controlling the New Student Admission (PPDB) in the Zoning System. Planning for the zoning system PPDB includes objectives, legal foundations, PPDB schedules, eligibility criteria determination, capacity determination, zoning determination, financing, and socialization. The organizational function of the zoning system PPDB involves the formation and assignment of committee tasks as well as communication and coordination systems managed by the committee. The implementation of the zoning system PPDB covers six aspects: registration, data input, data verification, selection, announcement of selection results, and enrollment. Lastly, regarding the supervision of the zoning system PPDB conducted in Jakarta, based on DKI Jakarta Regional Regulation Number 32/2021 on Technical Guidelines for PPDB, Chapter XV covers aspects of monitoring, evaluation, coaching, and supervision of PPDB.

Opportunity to Learn (OTL) is a measure of whether students and teachers have access to various resources that shape a quality school. It includes access to quality teachers, clean and safe facilities, quality books and learning materials, and school conditions that provide students with fairness and equality. Access to quality teachers, clean and safe facilities, and others will improve as the opportunity to learn increases (W. H. H. Schmidt & Maier, 2009). Furthermore, OTL has been developed to measure the "productivity of the school system" by examining the success of various school inputs on achievement (W. Schmidt et al., 2012).

METHODOLOGY

The researcher chose a qualitative approach to obtain detailed and in-depth information about the new student admission (PPDB) in the zoning system's role in improving learning opportunities for prospective high school students at SMA Negeri 28 and SMA Negeri 70 in Jakarta. This evaluation study uses the POAC (Planning, Organizing, Acting, and Controlling) management function analysis in the zoning system PPDB to assess its impact on students' learning opportunities. The research method used is an evaluative descriptive method because it can provide accurate and comprehensive analysis to reveal the necessary data.

The researcher employed three data collection techniques: interviews, observations, and document analysis. The researcher conducted direct observations at SMA Negeri 28 and SMA Negeri 70 in Jakarta to obtain primary and secondary data. Observations were made regarding the subjects and their behavior during interviews.

Interaction between subjects and the researcher and relevant matters that are considered can provide additional data to the interview results to find preliminary data. This observation is recorded in writing or through video/audio recordings. Documents are used as triangulation materials to check the data's consistency with reality. The goal is to enhance the data obtained through interviews and observations, making it suitable for sharpening the core issues regarding the management of new student admissions (PPDB) through the zoning system to improve learning opportunities. Interviews were conducted with the school principal, vice principal, operator, teachers, students, parents of students, and government or community representatives in the vicinity. Interviews focused on the activities of the zoning system PPDB at both research schools.

Data collection instruments for observation included school profiles, observation sheets used to observe the school environment and all its activities, including the school's location, school regulations, and so on. Interviews were conducted with the head of the South Jakarta Education Office, the head of the Pasar Minggu Education Department, the head of the Kebayoran Baru Education Department, the principal of SMAN 28 Jakarta, the principal of SMAN 70 Jakarta, the PPDB committees of SMAN 28 Jakarta and SMAN 70 Jakarta, teachers, parents of students, and relevant stakeholders as needed. Additionally, documentary research involved examining documents such as books, materials, registrations, data input, data verification, selection books, selection results, organizational structure, and other necessary documents during the research to supplement or reinforce the interview and observation data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Planning

The planning of new student admissions (PPDB) through the zoning system at the research site is carried out at the beginning of each new academic year to recruit new students. This aligns with the applicable rules, determining what needs to be implemented, when planning takes place, its execution and supervision, how it is done, and who is involved in the committee, all carefully considered while accounting for the present and future timeframes. It is done with appropriate strategies and tactics to achieve organizational goals.

This planning is recommended jointly by the highest authorities and is made by individuals who understand the organization and planning. Thus, it includes detailed planning, not devoid of implementation thinking, considering risk assessment, being simple, flexible, and practical. Additionally, it is based on the current and future reality.

This can be categorized as good planning, as Bafadal suggests that good planning consists of steps such as: (a) made by individuals who understand the organization, (b) made by individuals who understand planning, (c) accompanied by detailed planning, (d) not devoid of implementation thinking, (e) includes risk assessment thinking, (f) simple, flexible, and practical, (g) based on the current and future reality, (h) made together, (i) recommended by the highest authority (Bafadal, 2009).

This indicates that management has been implemented at the school where this research took place, starting with good planning. This is essential because planning is the initial stage that forms the foundation for the implementation of management in subsequent stages. This aligns with the concept of planning according to Hasibuan, stating that "Planning is the fundamental function of management because organizing, staffing, directing, and controlling must first be planned" (Hasibuan, 2001).

The implementation of planning at the school covers aspects such as goals, legal basis, PPDB schedule, determination of requirements, determination of capacity, zoning determination, financing, and socialization. Regarding goals, both high schools aim to ensure equal access to educational services for students, bridge the gap between the school environment and the family environment, eliminate exclusivity and discrimination in schools, especially public schools, assist in analyzing teacher needs and distribution, encourage the creativity of educators in teaching heterogeneous (diverse) students, and assist local governments in providing targeted assistance, both in terms of school facilities and the improvement of the quality of educators and educational staff, eliminating the labels of favorite and non-favorite schools to provide equal learning opportunities for every citizen to receive education in public schools and equal learning opportunities for various segments of the population to learn and receive education in quality schools close to their residences.

The objectives of new student admissions (PPDB) through the zoning system for the 2022/2023 academic year at these two high schools are formulated jointly by the PPDB committees at the schools before the new student admissions (PPDB) take place. Both high schools have planned the objectives of implementing the zoning system PPDB by dividing the areas based on the residences of prospective students to promote the even distribution and development of educational units in the Jakarta region, funded by the local government in the nearest areas to their residences.

The objectives of new student admissions are in line with the planning objectives made to ensure that every activity is directed and avoids unnecessary issues. These planning objectives are created based on the shared expectations and desires within an organization. As Hasibuan states, "the desired goals should be reasonable, rational, ideal, and sufficient" (Hasibuan, 2001).

The objectives of new student admissions (PPDB) through the zoning system for the 2022/2023 academic year at these two high schools are in line with the goals of PPDB set by the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education, Ministry of

Education and Culture (PDSPK Kemendikbud), which state that the objectives of new student admissions through the zoning system are to: (a) Ensure that the admission of new students is carried out objectively, transparently, accountably, nondiscriminatory, and justly to promote access to educational services. (b) Ensure the availability and readiness of educational units (especially public schools) to provide quality education. (c) Ensure equal access and quality education in every zone/area designated close to the students' residences. (d) Ensure the availability of competent educators and educational personnel supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure that can be provided and used jointly by all educational units in the designated area/zone. (e) Control and ensure the quality of graduates and conduct comparative and competitive monitoring of the learning process and results in measured and sustainable educational service areas (PDSPK Kemendikbud, 2018). These objectives are also in line with the research by Nurjaningsih and Qonita, which states that the goal of implementing the zoning system PPDB is to create education in Indonesia based on fairness and make every school the best school, thereby achieving equitable educational quality (Nurjaningsih & Qonita, 2019).

As for the legal basis of the 2022/2023 PPDB at the research site, it is based on the letter from the Secretary-General of the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 6998/A5/HK.01.04/2022 regarding the Implementation of PPDB for the 2022/2023 Academic Year. The implementation of PPDB for the 2022/2023 academic year is guided by and based on Ministerial Regulation Number 1 of 2021 on New Student Admissions (PPDB) for Kindergarten, Elementary School, Junior High School, and High School/Vocational School. Similarly, the policy at the regional government level in Jakarta is stipulated in Jakarta Provincial Regulation Number 43 of 2019 concerning New Student Admissions, which states that the PPDB for high schools uses inclusive pathways, affirmation pathways, achievement pathways, as well as zoning and non-zoning pathways for prospective students within the province. Specifically:

- a. Jakarta Provincial Regulation Number 21 of 2022 Concerning Amendments to Jakarta Provincial Regulation Number 32 of 2021 Concerning Technical Guidelines for New Student Admissions.
- b. Jakarta Provincial Regulation Number 440 of 2022 Concerning School Zone Lists for New Student Admissions in 2022.
- c. Jakarta Provincial Regulation Number 441 of 2022 Concerning the Capacity of Public Education Units for New Student Admissions in 2022.
- d. Decree of the Head of the Education Office Number e-0011 of 2022 Concerning the Process Flow of New Student Admissions for the 2022/2023 Academic Year.
- e. Decree of the Head of the Education Office Number e-0012 of 2022 Concerning the Implementation of New Student Admissions for the 2022/2023 Academic Year.

Next, regarding the PPDB schedule, it is arranged according to the Decree of the Head of the Education Office of the Jakarta Provincial Government. The preparations for PPDB start with the formation of the PPDB committee, the development of a work program, the creation of brochures and banners for socialization purposes, determination of capacity, and extensive socialization efforts to the community, including technical simulations conducted by the committee. The PPDB activities are carried out according to the schedule set for PPDB. The PPDB schedule at both schools consists of several phases, including registration or school selection, followed by the second phase, which is the selection process, announcement, and self-reporting phase. The PPDB schedule for the zoning system for high schools is conducted online, starting from June 27th to June 29th, 2022, for 24 hours each day. Registration is open from 08:00 AM and closes at 02:00 PM on the last day. The selection process is also conducted online, from June 27th to June 29th, 2022, for 24 hours each day, starting at 08:00 AM and closing at 02:00 PM on the last day.

Subsequently, the announcement phase is also done online and takes place on June 29th, 2022, at 05:00 PM. Moving on to the final phase, which is the self-reporting phase, it is conducted online from June 30th to July 1st, 2022, for 24 hours (self-reporting opens at 08:00 AM and closes at 02:00 PM on the last day). This means that the schedule for the implementation of New Student Admissions (PPDB) activities at the two public schools in this research is carried out in accordance with the PPDB schedule itself, as per the schedule issued by the government. The PPDB schedule consists of phases such as registration or school selection, the selection process, announcement, and self-reporting.

When examined from a theological perspective, the well-structured or programmed PPDB schedule aligns with the theology of Sanusi, as found in the Quran. Allah states, including in Surah Ash-Shoff verse 4, that "Indeed, Allah loves those who fight in His cause in a row as though they are a [single] structure joined firmly" (Religion, 2007).

Regarding the determination of requirements for the zoning system PPDB, it is established that prospective students must be at most 21 (twenty-one) years old on July 1st of the current year as proof. This is in line with the provisions found in the Ministry of Education and Culture's regulation on the requirements for high school PPDB. The requirements for prospective Grade X high school students are as follows: on July 1st of the current year, the age of the student should not exceed 21 (twenty-one) years, they should have completed Grade 9 of junior high school or an equivalent level, verified by a diploma or equivalent document indicating graduation, and have a birth certificate or a birth registration certificate from the authorized party, and be registered in the Family Card (KK) issued at least 1 (one) year before the start of the registration date (Jakarta, 2021).

This means that the requirements for high school PPDB are in accordance with the provisions in the Ministry of Education and Culture's regulation. The requirements for prospective Grade X high school students are as follows:

- a. Be at most 21 (twenty-one) years old on July 1st of the current year.
- b. Have completed Grade 9 of junior high school or an equivalent level, as evidenced by a diploma or another equivalent document.
- c. The age, as referred to in point 1, should be verified by a birth certificate or a birth registration certificate from the authorized party.
- d. Be registered in the Family Card (KK) issued at least 1 (one) year before the start of the registration date (Jakarta, 2021).

The determination of capacity for the zoning system PPDB in the two public high schools in Jakarta where the research is conducted is set in such a way that the capacity is equal to the number of classes available at each school. The maximum capacity for each class consists of 36 students, based on the domicile of the prospective students in relation to the targeted school. The determination of capacity also considers the age of prospective students, starting from the oldest to the youngest. This is a selection process to fulfill the capacity for each new student candidate (CPDB) and becomes the criteria for selection in the Zoning Pathway through highly competitive selection based on domicile and age.

The determination of the capacity for the Zoning PPDB Pathway is carried out with the following provisions: (a) The quota for the Zoning Pathway is set at 50% (fifty percent) of the capacity; (b) Students can only choose a school according to the list of school zones that have been determined. The determination of capacity in these two schools is carried out in accordance with the Decree of the Head of Education Number e-0011 of 2022, stating that the Zoning Pathway is implemented with the following provisions:

- a. The quota for the Zoning Pathway is set at 50% (fifty percent) of the capacity.
- b. Students can only choose a school according to the list of school zones that have been determined.
- c. The determination of the capacity of students in these two public high schools is based on the Jakarta Provincial Governor's Regulation No. 32 concerning Technical Guidelines for New Student Admissions, which specifies that each class can accommodate a maximum of 36 students.

The determination of the zoning for the zoning PPDB is done through the mechanism of establishing a quality zoning system based on three zone/region-based stages. The first mechanism involves the Classification Nomination stage, where schools are selected and classified based on their accreditation results by the National School/Madrasah Accreditation Agency (BAN S/M), National Examination (UN) results, Teacher Competency Test (UKG) results, and Education Quality Assurance

(PMP) results. Second, through the Capacity Enhancement stage, schools selected in the classification stage as educational units receiving nominations will receive zone/region-based treatment related to educational infrastructure and learning facilities, both quantitatively and qualitatively (improvement of classrooms, computer laboratories, power supply, internet, implementation of computer-based national exams, sanitation facilities, and more), as well as improving teacher capacity (qualification improvement, teacher training and certification, fulfilling teacher teaching hours, and more). Third, the Monitoring stage designates schools in the monitored area based on their zones/regions by KKG/MGMP/MKKS organizations with the school (SMA) as the center/base for schools within one zone/region. This aligns with the guidance from the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education, Ministry of Education and Culture (PDSPK)

In terms of PPDB financing, prospective students are not charged any fees for registering in the zoning system PPDB. Instead, the financing comes from the local government's revenue and expenditure budget and other legitimate non-binding sources of income, in accordance with the provisions of the applicable laws and regulations. The financing of the zoning system PPDB in both public high schools is in line with the Ministry of Education and Culture Regulation Number 51 of 2018, which is fully funded by the School Operational Assistance (BOS) fund. Therefore, applicants are not charged any fees. The financing of the zoning system PPDB in these two schools aligns with Jakarta Provincial Regulation Number 32/2021 on Technical Guidelines for PPDB, Chapter XIII Financing, Article 26, which states that the financing for the implementation of PPDB is charged to the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget and other legitimate non-binding sources of income in accordance with the provisions of the laws and regulations (Jakarta, 2021).

Furthermore, regarding the socialization of the PPDB for the 2022/2023 academic year in both schools, it was carried out by the schools to all school community members, the local community, and the wider public through various means, including websites, school posts, banners, social media, and banners.

2. Organization

The organization of PPDB at the research site is done through aspects of committee formation and task distribution, as well as communication and coordination systems. In terms of PPDB committee formation and task distribution, a School Principal is appointed through consultation with the school management. The organizational structure of the PPDB committee is based on needs and is aligned with applicable regulations. The committee's structure and tasks include responsibilities, chairpersons, secretaries, secretariat sections, registration sections, data sections, information service/complaint service sections, coordinator operators, operators, public information officers, cleanliness sections, security, documentation and equipment, and public information officers and verifiers.

As for the communication and coordination aspect, the committee works in a hierarchical manner, starting from communication and coordination within the school, to the Education Sub-District Office, and the Jakarta Provincial Education Office. The communication carried out at these schools for PPDB is facilitated through various channels, such as call centers, websites, and WhatsApp groups. This implies that there is effective communication and coordination between the schools and the government through the Jakarta Provincial Education Office. In Islam, consideration of benefits and advantages in its Sharia is paramount for the well-being of humans and their environment, as reflected in the six-value system of Sanusi's Theology regarding benefits, which is expressed in Surah Al-Baqarah: 219.

3. Implementation

The implementation of the zoning system PPDB in the two schools where this research is conducted has been carried out following the organizational planning, in line with the guidance from the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Indonesia, conducted simultaneously nationwide in all high schools. This includes several aspects: registration, data input, data verification, selection, announcement of selection results, and enrollment aspects. All aspects applied in these two schools align with the guidance from the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia. Registration is conducted through an online system. All prospective students who wish to register have three school choices and register at their first-choice school.

Prospective students can choose the zoning route during registration. Registration is carried out in both schools, and prospective students are required to bring the zoning route application form and the necessary documents. Registration can be done independently or collectively through their respective originating schools. This means that the learning opportunities for all prospective students in both schools are open to the public, taking into account the place of residence and the distance to the school.

For applicants or new prospective students in these two schools, they can choose the zoning route for students according to the regulations of the regional government's residential zones. In the first and second stages, services are provided online through the website <https://ppdb.jakarta.go.id> with a 24-hour information system. Furthermore, in the implementation of PPDB, online complaint posts are set up through WhatsApp (WA) or email to receive complaints, issues, and challenges.

4. Supervision

Both of the schools involved in this research have conducted supervision, which includes monitoring, coaching, evaluation, and oversight. Aspects of supervision in terms of monitoring are carried out daily at the schools through monitoring by the school principals. The PPDB supervision is conducted by the Government Internal Oversight Apparatus and the district education office to serve as a measure for assessing or monitoring all activities within the PPDB. Evaluation is carried out by the

education department through supervision or monitoring between the department's operators and the school's operators during the entry of data for new prospective students, and the evaluation involves examining the PPDB reports from the schools, which include information about accepted students, the school's capacity, the number of applicants, and students accepted each day. While supervision is conducted at both of these schools, it begins with supervision by the school principal, who is responsible for PPDB activities, followed by the government department responsible for education matters, the Department of Communication, Informatics, and Statistics of DKI Jakarta Province.

The supervision of the Zoning System PPDB conducted at both of these schools in the Jakarta region is in accordance with DKI Jakarta Regional Regulation Number 32/2021 on Technical Guidelines for PPDB. Chapter XV covers aspects of Monitoring, Evaluation, Coaching, and Oversight. Article 28 states that:

- a. The Governor conducts monitoring, evaluation, coaching, and oversight of the implementation of PPDB.
- b. Monitoring and evaluation as referred to in paragraph (1) are carried out by the department responsible for government affairs in the field of education.
- c. Monitoring and evaluation of the PPDB information system and network are carried out by the Department of Communication, Informatics, and Statistics of DKI Jakarta Province.
- d. Coaching for the implementation of PPDB is carried out by the Assistant for People's Welfare in the Regional Secretariat.

Supervision of the PPDB implementation is carried out by the Government Internal Oversight Apparatus (Jakarta, 2021). This supervision is also in line with Handoko (2015), who defines supervision as the process of ensuring that the goals of the organization and management are achieved. This relates to the manner in which activities are conducted in accordance with the planned objectives.

CONCLUSION

The research findings on the 2022/2023 school year Zoning System PPDB (Admission Selection Process) are as follows:

1. Planning was carried out in accordance with the applicable standards and regulations, as well as the directives from the Ministry of Education and Culture. Eight planning aspects were considered, including objectives, legal foundations, PPDB schedules, eligibility criteria determination, capacity determination, zoning determination, financing, and socialization.
2. Organizational efforts were implemented in line with theoretical principles and PPDB regulations, with a committee structure and task delegation according to expertise to facilitate effective communication and coordination.

3. The implementation was influenced by effective communication, adequate resources for PPDB execution, disposition, attitude, commitment to the task, and the existence of a bureaucratic structure implemented through registration and an online registration system based on government policy provisions, executed in two stages.
4. Oversight was conducted by school principals as the accountable party for PPDB activities, as well as the Jakarta Provincial Education Department, the Department of Communication, Informatics, and Statistics of DKI Jakarta Province, in accordance with the DKI Jakarta Regional Regulation Number 32/2021 regarding Technical Guidelines for PPDB.

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